

Mobile Decision Support for Amateur Astronomy

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Abstract:

Nowadays, there are many ways to take pictures of celestial objects such as the Sun, the Moon, planets of the solar system and Deep Sky Objects (DSOs). Combining small optical instruments (such as 60mm diameter refractors) with inexpensive CMOS cameras allows to practice astrophotography and Electronically Assisted Astronomy (EAA) with good results, while large-diameter instruments coupled with premium cameras help to obtain stunning images of planets, discover unknown DSO, or even detect transient objects. Recent smart telescopes allow to observe the sky in a comfortable way.

Despite the many solutions available, the astronomer is always faced with the same dilemmas before getting out the equipment, and sometimes hitting the road to launch all-night observations. Is the night sky clear enough? Is the selected observation site really interesting? There are tools for obtaining geolocalised but general information (such as the MeteoBlue site, which provides weather predictions and sky quality metrics), but the seasoned astronomer will often rely on experience (number of stars actually visible, for example), while the inexperienced astronomer may be disappointed with the results after one night's observation (e.g. because of high-altitude clouds, humidity, etc.).

As part of research projects at Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) about the application of AI for the Space domain, we are working on systems to analyze sky images in smartphones: they have now sensitive sensors, and built-in software able to construct wide-field astronomical images very efficiently. To this end, we have been capturing astronomical images with different smartphones for several years, during nights of heterogeneous quality (with or without clouds or wind, light pollution, etc). We are gradually annotating these images by rating them from 1 (poor quality) to 10 (excellent), and we are training Deep Learning models for Image Quality Assessment (IQA) with Tensorflow, favouring the least resource-intensive models. These models are then converted using appropriate frameworks (RTLite or CoreML) to be deployed into a dedicated mobile application (for Android or iOS).

This application could become a new decision-making tool for astronomers. For example, during a potential night observation at a particular site, the AI-powered application can take pictures, analyze them and assess whether the quality of the sky is satisfactory. It can help astronomers decide whether or not it's worth getting out the equipment to observe, if the site is interesting, and it can provide advices on celestial targets that can really be observed (i.e. bright and/or faint DSO).